

Shortbread

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Abstract— Shortbread is a cookie, made from Maida, sugar, butter, and corn flour. Other ingredients like ground rice flour or for changing the texture of shortbread added sometimes flour. From original recipe made many more modern recipes. Shortbread made using vegetable fat (Fat spread) and butter and chemical leaving agent giving different texture, chemical leaving agent like baking powder. Shortbread cookies are crispy and crunchy in texture. A Britain woman named Mrs. McLintock originated Shortbread first printed recipe, in 1736. Shortbread is widely consumed during Christmas, all around the world walkers shortbread brand are consume. Shortbread baking on 180°C to 220°C, for avoiding browning shortbread are baked on low temperature. After baked, it is look white, or a light golden brown. Shortbread are available in many shapes.

Index Terms— Shortbread, cookie, baking.

I. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To find chemical properties of Shortbread Ingredients.
- 2) To standardized recipe of shortbread.
- 3) To study the proximate analysis of prepared shortbread
- 4) To study the effect of storage.
- 5) To study organoleptic evaluation of prepared product

II. MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY

The present research entitled "STUDIES AND STANDARDIZATION OF SHORTBREAD WITH ADDED LEMONPEEL" was conducted in collaboration with the Department of food science and Technology and the Department of Food Science and technology college of Food Technology, Saralgaon Dr. Balasaheb sawant konkan krishi veedyapeeth Dapoli, during 2018-19.

A. RAW MATERIALS

All ingredients were purchase from local market Saralgaon.

Ingredients-refined wheat flour, corn flour, butter, lemon peel, sugar

B. Methodology

Flowchart for the Preparation of shortbread

III. PROCEDURE

A. Sieving

Sieving refined wheat flour, corn flour for remove impurities and wastage

B. Beating

Beating together butter, sugar, and lemon peel

C. Mixing

Addition of flour and mix properly

D. Prepare dough

Mixing batter properly and preparation of dough

E. Freezing

Keep dough for 30 min in freezing temperature

F. Sheet preparation

Prepare a flat sheet using roller

G. Molding

Cutting in shape by using molder.

H. Baking

Bake 180 °C -200°C for 15-20 minutes until they are a very light golden color

I. Cooling

After baking cool down shortbread at room temperature.

J. Packaging and Labeling

Packing 100gm shortbread in a box

K. Storage

Store at room temperature for further study

IV. FORMULATION OF SHORTBREAD

Sample	Maida	Butter	Sugar	corn flour	Lemon peel
S ₁	33.5	33.5	14.75	10.70	8
S ₂	33.5	33.5	14.75	12.70	6
S ₃	33.5	33.5	14.75	14.70	4

(Table 1: Formulation of shortbread)

S1 -Shortbread preparation variation with quantity of corn flour and lemon peel.

S2- Shortbread preparation variation with quantity of corn flour and lemon peel.

S3- Shortbread preparation variation with quantity of corn flour and lemon peel.

Sample S2 in shortbread preparation variation with quantity of corn flour and lemon peel is selected because good taste and texture.

V. STANDARDIZED RECIPE PREPARATION OF SHORTBREAD

Standardize recipe use three types of composition. Make variation in corn flour and lemon peel variation are show in table no.3.1 formulation of shortbread. Raw material are use in following composition Maida 33.5gm. Butter 33.5 gm. Sugar 14. 25gm.corn flour 12.75gm. & lemon peel 6gm. Standardize recipe are show in table no.3.2

(Table 2: Standardized recipe of shortbread)

Ingredients	Quantity (for 100g)
Maida	33.5
Butter	33.5
Sugar	14.25
Corn Flour	12.75
Lemon Peel	6

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result get during present investigation are presented & discussed under suitable caption & sub captions under.

1. Composition of raw material**1.1. Wheat flour (Refined)**

(Table: 3 Proximate Analysis of Wheat)

Constituents	Refined flour (Maida)	
	Wet Base	Dry Base
Moisture %	13.20	-
Protein %	10.10	11.6
Fat %	0.82	0.94
Ash %	0.65	0.75

From the results presented in Table 4.1 is revealed that the Protein, moisture, fat, crude fiber, Ash and carbohydrate content of refined flour were 13.20, 10.10, 0.82, 0.65, 0.50 and 74.73 per cent, respectively. Gupta and Pingale (1970) and Nagi and Bains (1983) and Zlaticeat al.(2011) Rana (2006)reported moisture, fat, protein, carbohydrate and crude fiber, ash. content of wheat flour in the ranges 6.6 to 11.60, 8.0 to 15.6, 1.4 to 2.3, 0.43 to 1.8, 74.1 to 79.0, 1.2 to 1.9 per cent, respectively. The values for moisture content were high and fat and crude fiber were lower in the present investigation than the reported values .However, the values for protein, ash and carbohydrate were in the range of reported values. The mineral contents in terms of mg/100g were calcium (71.30), Phosphorous (142.80) and iron (4.48). Bourne (1989) observed calcium content of 43 and 38 mg/100g in the flours obtained by 95 and 91 per cent extraction rate, respectively. Whereas Popli and Dhindsa (1980) reported the range of calcium from 64 to 139 mg/100g in improved varieties of wheat grown in Punjab and Haryana. Narayan (1991) found 139.42 mg phosphorous per 100g of wheat flour. The results of present investigation are very close to the results reported by earlier workers with regards to chemical composition of wheat flour.

(Table 4: Proximate Analysis of shortbread)

Parameter	Shortbread (S2)
Ash	1.0%
Moisture	4.0%
Fat	29.2g
Protein	5.3g
Carbohydrate	60.5g

Energy	526.0kcal
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The moisture content in Shortbread was found 4.0% to be and fat content was low 29.2%. Sugar Contain more carbohydrate than other parameters 60.5% and ash content of Shortbread was found to be 1.0% respectively.

The findings of the standard AOAC 2000 model showed that all chemical parameters were more or less identical.

2. Organoleptic evaluation of Shortbread

Different kinds of samples were developed from batter of mixture. The products were developed after mixing refined wheat flour, butter, sugar with corn flour and lemon peel and subjected to sensory evaluation. The results get that the mean score values for various sensory attributes viz., color, appearance, texture taste, and overall acceptability varied from 6 to 9.

The samples prepared were analyzed by 9 point hedonic scale and composite scoring test. Results obtained by composite scoring test were shown in Table no. 4.3. While, average sensory analysis data analyzed by 9 point hedonic scale were shown

Sample	Sensory Attributes				Overall Acceptability
	Color	Appearance	Texture	Taste	
Control	6.7	7.0	6.1	9	7.1
S1	8.1	8.5	78.0	8.2	8.3
S2	8.0	8.5	7.9	8.1	8.2
S3	8.0	8.5	7.8	8.0	8.1

(fig 1: Graph on sensory evaluation No.1)

Prepared Shortbread was evaluated for organoleptic characteristics on the basis of colour, texture, taste and overall acceptability by a panel judges, academic staff members of College of Food Technology and comprised of postgraduate students ,Saralgaon,Thane. Sample was graded on the basis of a hedonic scale of nine points judges are asked to rate the brand on 9 point hedonic scale with suitable

descriptive terms ranging from 9` like extremely to 1` particularly hate

3. Effect of storage on organoleptic properties of Shortbread

The product was analyzed for its shelf life by keeping it at room temperatures. It was found that the product kept at room temperature had shelf life above 60 days because the microbial growth was slow in the sample kept at room temperature. The sample kept at room temperature had shelf life more than 60 day. Effect of storage on organoleptic properties of Shortbread Table No.4.4 Based on results of shortbread organoleptic evaluation, Sample S2 was packed in a paper box and stored for a specific 15day time interval at room temperature (30°C) up to 60 days.

The above table data revealed that during the storage period of 60 days (Room Temperature) there was a significant change in sensorial parameters. Changes in organoleptic properties were observed at an interval of 15 days. Fresh shortbread was found to be the highest score (8.5) compared to Shortbread stored.

It was evident from the above table that the lowest color score (8.3) registered on the 60th day of processing. During shortbread processing from 0 to 60 days, there was a decrease in sensory rating for overall acceptability (8.5) found to be with fresh sample at Equalize. Nevertheless, the sensory score for texture, taste and overall acceptability were significantly reduced on the 60th day of storage (8.1)was observed but liked moderately by the panel members

Shortbread				
Sample	Shortbread(s ₂)			
Storage days	appearance and Color	Texture	Taste or Flavor	Overall acceptability
0	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
15 Days	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
30 Days	8.4	8.3	8.4	8.5
45 Days	8.4	8.2	8.3	8.3
60 Days	8.3	8.1	8.1	8.2

(Table 6: Effect of storage on organoleptic properties of Shortbread)

VII. TECHNO ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY

On the basis of Table no 7 that the cost of 1kg of Shortbread packed in pastry box was of Rs.224.55(Rs.22.47for100gm). The available Shortbread in market i.e. walker shortbread, costing approximately Rs. 25/100gm. The above Approximation cost of prepared Shortbread was found to be compare cheaper than the commercial marketed Shortbread. In addition to this, The Shortbread prepared proved its energy function over the sample of the market. Consumers would thus prefer it and developed cereal-based baked product technology could be exploited commercially for entrepreneurs and stakeholders.

Ingredients	Quantity	Cost/unit	Cost(rs)
Refined wheat flour	335gm	28/kg	9.38
Butter	335gm	400/kg	132
Sugar	142.5gm	35/kg	4.98
Corn flour	127.5gm	40/kg	5.10
Lemon peel	60gm	2/piece	19
Total raw material cost			170.46
Total Processing cost@20% of raw material			34.092
Packaging box	30 shortbread		20
2Rs./10box			
Production cost for 1kg of shortbread			224.55
Production cost for 33.33gm per shortbread			7.49

(Table : 7 Techno economic feasibility)

VIII. SUMMARY

Main reason of choosing the shortbread is specification such as texture and suitable colour, easy production, no need for control environment during storage and the availability of all the components. The main purpose to preparation of shortbread is to avoid junk food. Each biscuit provide maximum kcal energy in minimum or less weight. The shortbread use for snacks. The shortbread is used as RTE Food, also used in traveling & used for travelling people. The shortbread is used for the fast food are able to fulfill the daily morning meal. Effect has been made to formulate and standardized the production of shortbread and result obtained are summarized as follows. The physicochemical properties were obtained evident from the moisture content in shortbread was found to be 4.0 per cent. in this shortbread

content higher amount of energy. Physicochemical, microbial and textural changes were studied in shortbread. The physicochemical and microbiological properties of shortbread at having various collection points in various formulations. Sensory evaluation of shortbread was carried out & score recorded was s2 sample observed higher score of colour, texture, appearance and taste of the sample significantly affected with addition of various formulations. Sample s2 like very much having more good taste and texture content was selected for further study. Sample s2 was observed higher score followed by s1 and s3 samples. The Proximate analysis was carried out and score recorded was obtained s2 sample observed per cent of moisture is 4.0%, fat content is 29.2%, protein is 5.3% carbohydrate is higher than other parameters is 60.5% .the ash is 1%, the Energy value is 526.0kcal. Storage effect on product was good on up to 60 days in room temperature was carried out & score recorded was s2 sample. The significant changes were noticed in colour, texture, appearance and taste during 60 days of storage. Similarly scores for all the sensory attributes a slight decrease in colour, taste, texture and chewiness and overall acceptability was observed with storage in room temperature. Assessment & techno-economic feasibility of shortbread production was carried out the cost was 449.1 per 2 kg calculated by considering the current local market prices of raw materials including processing costs and it was profitable as compared to the market shortbread sample.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, it emerges that the formulation & standardization of recipe for Shortbread was carried out successfully prepared by using Maida, Sugar, Butter and other ingredient. The health benefit Lemon peel and Freshness Flavour are well known so the product is having some enrichment. With respect to the organoleptic properties, Shortbread fortified was excellent of all the Shortbread produced, accompanied by an increased protein, fat and energy content of nutritional quality in Shortbread. That form of nutrient / enrichment added value certainly helps to provide a good energy source. So, in accepts & quality, the product can satisfy the consumer.

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